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Two-year colleges: Motivational factors among older engineering students

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ABSTRACT

Two-year technological colleges provide learning opportunities for students from the socio-economic periphery or students with a relatively low level of achievement. This study quantitatively examined the factors driving older students to study electronics at a leading two-year college in Israel. Sixteen older students participated in the study. The students completed an anonymous close-ended questionnaire, based on the *SRQ-A* and the *SIMS* scales. The findings indicate that the older students are primarily driven by interest in the studies (intrinsic motivation) and by recognising their inherent value (identified regulation). However, an additional factor with a notable weight is external regulation, according to which, some of the students are studying electronics for lack of another choice.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering education research, Attractiveness of engineering education, Gender and diversity

Keywords: Electrical engineering education, Two-year colleges, Motivation, Older students

INTRODUCTION

Two-year technological colleges offer practical engineering training, allowing their graduates to directly integrate into various industrial fields, such as electronics, biotechnology, and mechanical engineering. Both in the United States and Israel, students at these colleges often belong to disadvantaged groups, or are with relatively low academic ability [1].

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In Israel, there are two educational frameworks for studying towards a practical engineering degree: the first is for younger students, who continue to post-secondary studies directly from high school, and the second is for older students, who have taken some time out from their schooling. In this paper, we focus on the latter track, supervised by the Israeli Ministry of Economy and Industry.

Nowadays, there is a severe lack of two-year college graduates in Israel, especially in the field of electronics. This lack partially originates from the decrease in the number of those expressing an interest in studying at two-year technological colleges [2]. The literature, however, is meagre [1] and mainly deals with specific pedagogical aspects relevant to engineering students at Israeli two-year colleges [3-4].

The aim of the research was to investigate the motivational factors driving older students to study electronics at a two-year college.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Motivation refers to a person's will to invest resources in a certain activity, even when it involves difficulties. Self-determination theory [5-6], which is currently one of the leading motivation theories and has constituted the theoretical framework for many studies in engineering education (e.g., [7-10]), served as the theoretical framework for this research.

The theory argues that the factors motivating an individual's behaviour are suited on a continuum. Intrinsic motivation, originating from the interest and pleasure an individual derives from the behaviour is positioned at one end of the spectrum, while extrinsic motivation is suited at the other pole of the continuum.

Extrinsic motivation includes various types of regulation; the most important ones are described below:

- Identified regulation which results from the identification of a value (other than interest and pleasure) involved in the behaviour.
- Introjected regulation which stems from the desire to fulfil the expectations of important people to the person or from considerations of personal prestige.
- External regulation which originates from the desire to receive a reward for the behaviour, or alternatively, from the fear of punishment.

The primary motivational factors are shown in *Fig. 1*.

According to self-determination theory [5-6], the more intrinsic the sources of the motivational factors – the higher the quality of a person's motivation. The theory claims that supporting an individual's three innate needs fosters high-quality motivation. These basic needs are:

- Autonomy – feeling a person's behaviour was not imposed on him/her.
- Competence – feeling a person is able to fulfil challenging objectives.
- Relatedness – being accepted and be part of a group.

Fig. 1. Primary motivational factors

2 RESEARCH GOAL AND METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study was to examine the factors motivating older students to study electronics at a two-year college.

Sixteen second-year older students at a leading two-year technological college in Israel took part in the study. These students were studying electronics in a programme supervised by the Ministry of Economy and Industry, mentioned above.

The students completed an anonymous close-ended questionnaire. This five-point Likert-like questionnaire, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”, was based on the *SRQ-A* (Self-Regulation Questionnaire – Academic) [11] and the *SIMS* (Situational Motivation Scale) scales [12]. The questionnaire included twenty statements which reflected the four major motivational factors, as defined by self-determination theory. Examples are given in *Table 1*.

The statements were validated by two experts in engineering education. Cronbach’s alphas show good internal consistency, as indicated below: 0.84 (intrinsic motivation), 0.80 (identified regulation), 0.78 (introjected regulation), and 0.86 (external regulation).

Table 1. Questionnaire statements: Examples

Motivation	Regulation	Statement
Intrinsic		I am studying electronics because I think the studies are interesting
Extrinsic	Identified	I am studying electronics because I think working in electronics would be a good job for me
	Introjected	I am studying electronics because my friends are studying electronics I am studying electronics because I want people to think I am smart
	External	I am studying electronics because I do not have a choice

3 FINDINGS

The analysis reveals that students are primarily motivated by intrinsic motivation ($M=76.88$; $SD=10.78$, where the mean score M is between 20 and 100) and identified regulation ($M=68.93$; $SD=11.89$). External regulation is in the third place ($M=47.08$; $SD=17.46$) and introjected regulation is the less important factor ($M=41.25$; $SD=12.58$).

A comparison to the motivational factors among sophomore electrical engineering students from a leading university in Israel [13], shown in Fig. 2, indicates a significant difference ($p<0.05$) between the two groups in relation to external regulation. This gap, in favour of the first, is characterised by a medium-large effect size ($d=0.62$).

Fig. 2. Motivational factors: Mean score

4 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

Two-year technological colleges provide learning opportunities for students from the socio-economic periphery or students with a relatively low level of achievement. This study quantitatively examined the factors motivating older students to study electronics at a leading two-year college in Israel.

According to the findings, older electronics students at the two-year college are motivated by interest in the studies (intrinsic motivation) and by recognising their inherent value (identified regulation). An additional factor with a considerable weight is external regulation, according to which, some of the students study electronics for lack of any other option. The significant gap between the university students and the two-year college students in relation to this motivational factor may indicate that the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are only partially met at the technological college.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the study described in this article was the first to investigate the motivational factors for studying electronics in older students at two-year colleges. Beyond this theoretical contribution to the meagre body of knowledge on the subject, these results could contribute to the recognition of problems inherent to this course of study and to finding ways to increase its attractiveness both in Israel and in other countries that have a tertiary technological education system.

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